

Data Interfaces at CEDA

Stephen Pascoe
(*Stephen.Pascoe@stfc.ac.uk*)

Overview

- Context
 - Standards: CF-NetCDF, OGC Web Services, INSPIRE
 - Data diversity challenges
- Solutions
 - Visualisation
 - Subsetting and Aggregation
 - Federated Access Control
 - Bespoke data-centric applications

Standards Environment

- Community Standards
 - File formats and protocols: NetCDF, OPeNDAP
 - File-level metadata conventions: CF-NetCDF
- Geoinformatics
 - Open Geospatial Consortium standards
 - Web Map Service (WMS)
 - Web Coverage Service (WCS)
 - Web Feature Service (WFS)
 - Web Processing Service (WPS)
- INSPIRE
 - ISO191xx

Metadata Workflow: Top down / Bottom Up

Context Metadata

Use Metadata

Interoperable visualisation

Opportunities for the “NetCDF/OPeNDAP Platform”

History UKCIP09 User Interface

Requirements

- Map and non-map plots
- Interactive and configurable
- Long-running tasks
 - Large data extractions
 - Secondary simulations (Weather Generator)
- Resilient to variable load

Service Orientated Architecture

UKCP09 Deployment

CEDA-WPS Web Client

PlotTitle Please insert a value of type: string.

BoundingBox Current Bounding Box:
 North :
 West : East :
 South :

Please select a valid bounding box with the following geographical extent: -30, -30, 30, 30

Click this button when you are happy with your

The UI automatically generates submission forms for each process. This includes bounding box, date/time, float, integer and string types.

COWS Web Processing Service

Distributed Processing in an OGC / Pylons framework

[Home](#) [Capabilities](#) [View](#) [Submit](#) [Jobs](#) [Documentation](#) [Login](#)

Define your inputs

Please complete the form below to submit a request to the CEDA Web Processing Service. Note that some processes are restricted to registered users only. Click the 'Submit' button to submit your request.

This process includes arguments for which the possible values are dependent on calls to an external process. Please click the 'Update form' button at any time to update the argument options based on the selections you have made.

Dataset	<input type="text" value="-- Please select --"/> <input type="text" value="/usr/local/cows_venv/local_dists/cows_wps/cows_wps/tests/data/cdml/eg_hadcm3.xml"/> <input type="text" value="/usr/local/cows_venv/local_dists/cows_wps/cows_wps/tests/data/cdml/eg_cdml.xml"/>	This field is dynamic, please select other options then click 'Update form' to populate the form field. Then please select an item from the list.
Variable	<input type="text" value="-- Please select --"/> <input type="text" value="theta"/> <input type="text" value="u"/>	This field is dynamic, please select other options then click 'Update form' to populate the form field. Then please select an item from the list.
Description	<input type="text" value="long"/>	Please select an item from the list.

Click to update the options above based on the selections you have made.

Click this button when you are happy with your selections.

Operational Service MIDAS

- New Service at BADC (beta)
- UK Met Office MIDAS database
- Land surface observations data from the Met Office station network
- daily and hourly weather measurements
- Extract by UK county of bounding box
- CSV output

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `ceda-wps2.badc.rl.ac.uk/submit/form?proc_id=ExtractUKStationData`. The page contains a form for data extraction with the following fields:

- StartDateTime**: . Instruction: Please insert a date/time field in the format YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ss such as 2009-01-01T00:00:00.
- EndDateTime**: . Instruction: Please insert a date/time field in the format YYYY-MM-DDTHH:mm:ss such as 2009-01-01T00:00:00.
- OutputTimeChunk**: . Instruction: Please select an item from the list.
- BBox**: Current Bounding Box: [-6.8,55.5,-5.1,57.5]. West: [-6.8], South: [55.5], East: [-5.1]. Instruction: This input is optional. Please select a valid bounding box within the following geographical extent: -12.0, 49.0, 3.0, 61.0. A map of the UK is shown with a red bounding box.
- Counties**: . Instruction: This input is optional. Multiple inputs are allowed. Please select one or more items from the list. The dropdown menu lists: ABERDEENSHIRE, ALDERNEY, ANGUS, ANTRIM, ARGYLL (IN HIGHLAND REGION), ARGYLL (IN STRATHCLYDE REGION), ARGYLLSHIRE, ARMAGH, ASCENSION IS.

Test Beds: MashMyData

- Proof-of-concept web portal
- Scientists will be able to simultaneously visualize data from many sources, including their own uploaded data
- Scientists will be able to perform simple quantitative comparison calculations
- Data access will require Authentication and Authorisation

Test Beds: MashMyData

OGC and OPeNDAP Services in a Secured Workflow

1) A user accesses the MashMyData Portal

2) They select some datasets for an intercomparison operation requiring a process run by the WPS.

3) The portal requests the BADC's WPS execute this calculation on its behalf, but it responds indicating that access credentials are required to access secured datasets

4) The portal prompts the user to sign in with OpenID

6) The portal uses the certificate acquired from the Credential Translation Service to authenticate with the WPS

5) Once the user has signed in, the portal can translate their authenticated status by obtaining a short-lived certificate representing them from the Credential Translation Service - This credential can be used by the Portal to authenticate the user on their behalf with other services.

7) The portal also provisions a Delegation Service with a proxy certificate configuring it to enable the WPS to perform credential retrievals

8) The WPS can retrieve a proxy certificate from the Delegation Service to enable it to authenticate with an OPeNDAP service on behalf of the user.

9) When the WPS has completed execution of the given job it exposes the results to the Portal for retrieval.

History

OGC Web Services at CEDA

- CEDA has developed web portals based on OGC Web Services since 2006
 - WMS clients and servers
 - WCS/WFS for complex GML features (CSML)
- NERC Data Grid
- NERC Portals Project
- ISIC Visualisation

Thanks

